

A HISTORICAL ANALYSIS OF HARMONIC PROGRESSIONS USING CHORD EMBEDDINGS

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ABSTRACT

This study focuses on the exploration of the possibilities arising from the application of an NLP word-embedding method (Word2Vec) to a large corpus of musical chord sequences, spanning multiple musical periods. First, we analyse the clustering of the embedded vectors produced by Word2Vec in order to probe its ability to learn common musical patterns. We then implement an LSTM-based neural network which takes these vectors as input with the goal of predicting a chord given its surrounding context in a chord sequence. We use the variability in prediction accuracy to quantify the stylistic differences among various composers in order to detect idiomatic uses of some chords by some composers. The historical breadth of the corpus used allows us to draw some conclusions about broader patterns of changing chord usage across musical periods from Renaissance to Modernity.

1. INTRODUCTION

Algorithmic approaches to music usually come in two flavors: music information retrieval (MIR) aims at extracting relevant patterns from musical signals (e.g. audio recordings, MIDI files, or images of scores) and improve the performance on certain specific tasks, such as genre or composer classification, automatic playlist generation, optical music recognition and more. Computational music analysis, on the other hand, aims at using data-driven methods to study the domain of music in order to develop a deeper understanding of its cultural and historical diversity, or implications for its perception and cognition.

This study bridges the two approaches by applying the machine-learning (ML) methods often employed for the task of chord prediction in MIR to a large corpus of symbolic chord sequences. However, our goal is not to globally optimize chord prediction in this dataset. Rather, we use the chord-prediction task as a benchmark measure

for investigating stylistic characteristics of different composers in the dataset. We suppose that the historical dimension in particular affects stylistic differences which, in turn, should be reflected in the performance of a (globally constant) chord predictor. In other words, assuming a fixed model for chord prediction, how does its performance change given historically varying input? What conclusions can we draw from this perspective?

In the remainder of the paper, we first summarize recent related work (Section 2). We then describe the dataset used in our study (Section 3), as well as our specific application of the three ML approaches in more detail (Section 4). We report two important results (Section 5): that clustering in an embedding space reveals functional relations between chords, and that changes in performance of our chord-prediction model (dependent on composer and historical time) indicate fundamental changes in the usage of harmony.

2. RELATED WORK

Our study draws on a dataset of symbolic musical chord sequences and uses three fundamental machine learning building blocks: word embeddings, clustering, and Recurrent Neural Networks (RNNs).

Word embedding is a popular technique in Natural Language Processing (NLP) which learns a mapping of words to vectors in a low-dimensional *embedding space* from a *corpus* of texts, which is supposed to contain sufficient information on the semantic relationships between words. The mapping is such that the relative positions of the vectors (hopefully) reflect these semantic relationships. The precise learning of this mapping is dependent on the specific method used. We use Word2Vec [1]. In Word2Vec, words often appearing in similar contexts are mapped to close points in the embedding space, according to their cosine distance.

Previous work has used Word2Vec successfully for modeling aspects of the musical language. In [2], the authors show that a simple approach of splitting musical scores into short slices containing note presence information is able to capture some simple features such as tonal proximity. Later, in [3], a similar slicing procedure is used on a

larger corpus that re-affirms Word2Vec’s ability to model musical concepts such as tonal relationships between musical keys. In [4], the authors learn an embedding space in a similar way, but use as input multi-hot vectors of note presence, rather than one-hot encodings of unique symbols (as in the standard Word2Vec). In contrast to these efforts, our work takes annotated chord symbols as input, thus enabling us to model information at a much higher level of abstraction by eliminating information spurious to the harmonic structure such as short passing tones and ornamentation.

Clustering is a well-known unsupervised learning primitive, which works by grouping together close points in a space, and is used to extract information about the points that might be contained in their coordinates. We use hierarchical clustering [5] with cosine distance to analyze the structural properties of our resulting chord embedding space. This hierarchical approach (as opposed to a more naive clustering approach like K-means [6]) has the benefit of allowing us to investigate clusters at different levels of granularity without needing to fine-tune any hyperparameters. Previous work has also investigated the clustering of musical embeddings, using explicitly trained chordal embeddings (e.g., [2,3]), chord clusters induced through training for a different task (e.g., [7, 8]), or clustering of larger groups of chords (e.g., [9]).

RNNs are widespread tools in NLP, particularly in the field of word prediction with their Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) [10] variant. LSTMs are particularly suited to this task because of their structure, involving a *forget gate*, which solves the *short-term memory* problem, typical of traditional RNNs. Similar work shows how they can be successfully employed in musical contexts, for “next-slice” modeling [4, 11], as well as for chord prediction [7, 12], and cadence identification [13]. While the cited works try to maximize prediction accuracy as much as possible, our goal is slightly different. Of course, we do want the models to perform as well as possible, but our main focus in the current work is instead to investigate the change in prediction performance across historical time (enabled by our expansive corpus), and to try draw musical conclusions from this.

3. DATA

The dataset at our disposal, used for embedding, clustering, and chord prediction, consists of 4045 chord progressions in pieces by 24 Western classical composers, spanning the wide historical range from the Renaissance to 20th-century Modernism. The data has been derived from harmonic annotations using the syntax presented in [14–17]. For this study, the labels have been simplified in order to decrease the size of the chord vocabulary and to remove sparsity in our data. The pieces have been partitioned into local key segments that are either in the major or the minor *mode* (i.e., they contain no modulations), and chords are expressed relative to the tonic of that mode. Specifically, chords are represented by their *root* (expressed as a Roman numeral referring to the scale degree of the mode) and their *quality* (major, minor, dimin-

ished, or augmented; 7th chords are reduced to their corresponding triad). Because of this representation, the chord vocabulary is *potentially* infinite because the seven scale degrees of the two modes can be preceded by arbitrarily many accidentals. In particular, this allows us to distinguish enharmonically equivalent triads, such as $\#III:MAJ$ and $bIII:MAJ$ that may entail different harmonic functions. Applied chords have been reduced to be directly related to the tonic of the mode, e.g. “ vii°/V ” is translated to “ $\#iv^\circ$ ” and represented as $\#IV:DIM$. Thus, the chord sequences in our dataset are of the form

- MAJOR; I:MAJ, II:MIN, V:MAJ, . . . , or
- MINOR; I:MIN, II:DIM, III:MAJ, . . . ,

where mode and chord labels are separated by a semicolon and chords within a progression are separated by commas. The average length of a chord sequence is 31 chords for major sequences and 28 chords for minor sequences. Since the roots of chords are expressed in relative notation, i.e. as the distance to the tonic, an F major chord is represented as $IV:MAJ$ if the chord sequence is in C major, but as $III:MAJ$ if it is in D minor. Following these reductions, there are 81 distinct chords in major sequences, and 77 different chords in minor sequences in our data.

As one can observe in Figure 1, the amount of data at our disposal varies greatly across composers and historical periods. Note, for example, that no chord sequences in the major mode are available for Sweelinck. Great care has thus to be taken when generalizing our results to the entire oeuvre of these composers or the historical periods they represent. The data is available at <https://github.com/DCMLab/chordembeddings-smc2021>.

4. METHODOLOGY

4.1 Chord embedding

Our first processing step, serving as a basis for the two downstream tasks of clustering and chord prediction, is the application of Word2Vec [1]—specifically its implementation in the Gensim library [18]—which takes as input “sentences” (in our case, major or minor sequences) of “words” (in our case, chord labels). We treat major and minor chord sequences as independent and never include chord sequences from both modes in conjunction. Thus, in the following, when we say “train/test on all sentences/sections of a composer” or “train/test on a composer”, we implicitly mean that those sections are all in the same mode.

Word2Vec has four hyperparameters to tune: *size*, *window*, *sg* (skip-gram), and *min_count*. *size* determines the dimension of the embedding space. To avoid overfitting, it should be less than the size of the vocabulary, i.e. the number of distinct chords in the corpus. In our case, the vocabulary size varies considerably, between 20 and 100 chord types per composer within either of the two modes. *window* defines the “width” of the context, i.e. how many chords, to the left and to the right, constitute the context of the current chord. The binary parameter *sg*

Figure 1. Total number of non-unique chord labels used by each composer, split between major and minor sequences. Composers are ordered by year of death (from oldest at the top to more recent at the bottom).

1 is short for “skip-gram” and selects the training algorithm:
 2 it can be either “continuous bag of words” (CBOW, i.e.
 3 guessing the target word from its context), or “skip-gram”
 4 (guessing the context given the target word). `min_count`
 5 sets a minimum absolute frequency a chord must have in
 6 order to be kept in the corpus. Since our corpus contains
 7 a Zipf-like distribution, this allows us to remove from the
 8 result the numerous irrelevant mappings of rare chords.

9 For all of our experiments, we exclude rare chords, as
 10 the model is unable to learn a stable embedding for such
 11 chords, making any relevant conclusion impossible. We
 12 therefore set `min_count = 50` (since the most common
 13 chords have absolute frequencies of hundreds, if not thou-
 14 sands), which led to a vocabulary size of 32. The `size` of
 15 the embedding space was then chosen to be 5 (alternatives
 16 were essentially equivalent). We set `window = 2` (again,
 17 other values led to similar results), and finally, we chose
 18 to use skip-gram rather than CBOW embeddings, because
 19 this led to more interpretable results.

20 4.2 Clustering

21 A first application of the mapping learned by Word2Vec is
 22 clustering, which is used to detect musical patterns. As is
 23 understandable from the properties of the mapping, chords
 24 appearing in the same cluster are likely to often appear in
 25 similar contexts. For this task, it is very difficult to carry
 26 out an objective, quantitative model evaluation. Therefore,
 27 we choose hyperparameters based on how much the out-
 28 come corresponds to music-theoretical intuitions. For ex-

29 ample, we expect, when only training on major sections,
 30 that tonics and dominants are embedded close to each
 31 other, since they constitute the most basic musical pattern
 32 imaginable, as discussed in [15], and therefore often occur
 33 in very similar contexts.

34 *Hierarchical clustering* works by recursively merging
 35 the pair of clusters C_i and C_j (starting from singletons)
 36 that are the closest to each other according to some dis-
 37 tance metric. We use *cosine distance*, commonly used
 38 for vector embedding spaces. The recursion stops when
 39 the minimum distance between clusters is above a given
 40 `distance_threshold`, or when only a single cluster
 41 remains.

42 The fact that this algorithm can work with cosine
 43 distance is ideal to detect similarities in a Word2Vec
 44 embedding space. Moreover, it is able to capture
 45 clusters of any shape. One might argue that a
 46 choice of `distance_threshold` can be quite arbi-
 47 trary. However, this can be avoided by setting the
 48 `distance_threshold` to some large value (thus merg-
 49 ing all clusters into one), and then plotting a dendro-
 50 gram of all possible mergers. A dendrogram (e.g., Figure 3)
 51 is a depiction of the nested clusters produced by this method:
 52 it clearly shows all the mergers $C_i - C_j$ that happened,
 53 and the distance associated to them.

54 4.3 Chord prediction

55 Another use of the mapping provided by Word2Vec is the
 56 chord prediction task. LSTMs are an improvement over the
 57 classic RNN design that solve its *short-term memory* prob-
 58 lem (caused by the well-known *vanishing gradient* prob-
 59 lem): this allows them to effectively track long-term de-
 60 pendencies in sequential data. They are commonly used in
 61 NLP to predict the next word in a sentence.

62 We implemented an LSTM-based neural network for
 63 chord prediction, which trains on a *training corpus* (all
 64 sentences from a set of *training composers* for a given
 65 mode) and is tested on a *test corpus* (all sentences from a
 66 single *test composer* for that mode). For the LSTM exper-
 67 iments, the Word2Vec embedding is retrained using only
 68 the training corpus. Thus, we test how well-predictable
 69 chords in musical sequences by a composer are given the
 70 knowledge about chord sequences by all other composers.
 71 The metric used is the simple accuracy: the fraction of
 72 correctly-predicted chord occurrences, either overall or
 73 grouped by chord. We use the overall accuracy results for
 74 a single test composer to see how “predictable” they are,
 75 from what we learned from the training composers. We
 76 use the same results, split by chord, to investigate which
 77 chords are easier to predict and which are used more id-
 78 iomatically (and are thus more difficult to predict).

79 The LSTM design is shown in Figure 2, and is structured
 80 as follows. Given a target chord (c_n in the figure), a first
 81 LSTM layer takes as input the concatenation of the embed-
 82 ded vectors of chords within some window of the target
 83 chord (shown as black circles in the figure with a window
 84 size of 2). A linear layer then maps the LSTM’s output
 85 vector to a vector of length `n_vocab` (where `n_vocab` is
 86 the number of distinct chords), with a final softmax activa-

Figure 2. Diagram for the predictor network.

tion.

For the chord prediction experiments, we use the same Word2Vec parameters as above, although the embeddings are recalculated for each test composer. For both training and testing the LSTM, we take care to remove any data points which contain any chord (either as input or as the target) that falls below Word2Vec’s `min_count` (in the training corpus). For training the LSTM, we use the Adam optimizer [19] with mean squared error (MSE) for the loss. We train all results for 2 epochs (this was enough for them to converge in all cases).

5. RESULTS

Our results imply two main findings: 1) clustering chords in the embedding space reveals meaningful functional relations between many of them; 2) chord prediction accuracy exhibits historical trends.

5.1 Clustering reveals functional chord relations

First, we report the results we obtained by applying hierarchical clustering on the embedded chords from the major and minor sections of all composers in the corpus. We visualize the hierarchical clustering in the embedding spaces for the major and the minor mode in dendrograms in Figures 3 and 4, respectively. As mentioned before, distances in embedding spaces are inherently difficult to interpret in general. However, many of the resulting clusters are quite well interpretable in various ways.

The resulting clusters for chord sequences for both modes reveal two fundamental tonal relations: functional *equivalence* and functional *difference* [20–22]. This extends earlier similar findings on functional categories restricted to J. S. Bach’s chorales and based on chord bigrams [23]. Below we list a number of notable functional chord relations that can be found in our clusterings.

5.1.1 Functional equivalence

Chords that share common tones may be regarded as functionally equivalent. Functionally equivalent chords include *relative* and *parallel* chords, as well as other *common-tone* relations [24]. Two chords are each other’s relative if they are the tonics of two keys that have the same key signature (e.g. V:MAJ and III:MIN in a major key). A major and minor chord are parallel if they have the same root (e.g. II:MAJ and II:MIN). Chords may also retain the same function, if they share a number of tones (e.g. V:MAJ and

Figure 3. Dendrogram for chord embeddings in major.

Figure 4. Dendrogram for chord embeddings in minor.

1 #VII: DIM jointly form a dominant seventh chord in any
2 minor key).

3 In the major mode (Figure 3), the relative chords
4 that are clustered together are II: MIN and IV: MAJ
5 as well as IV: MIN and bVI: MAJ. The parallel chords
6 are VII: MAJ and VII: MIN, and the chords in-
7 volved in other common-tone relations are V: MAJ
8 and VII: DIM; II: MAJ and #IV: DIM; II: DIM
9 and IV: MIN; III: MAJ and #V: DIM; VI: MIN and
10 #IV: DIM as well as III: DIM and #I: DIM.

11 In minor (Figure 4), the relative chords close to
12 one another in the embedding space are VII: MIN
13 and bII: MAJ; IV: MAJ and II: MIN; as well as
14 IV: MIN and VI: MAJ. The parallel chords in mi-
15 nor are #VI: MAJ and #VI: MIN; and, finally, the
16 chords with other common-tone relations are II: DIM
17 and #VII: DIM; I: DIM and III: MIN; V: DIM and
18 VII: MIN; #III: MIN and #I: DIM; as well as
19 #IV: MAJ and #IV: DIM.

20 Overall, in our chord embeddings, the relative and
21 common-tone relations are much more frequent than par-
22 allel relations, which is to be expected, since the latter in-
23 volves a change of mode and the sections from which the
24 chords are drawn are precisely defined as staying within
25 one mode (major or minor, notwithstanding potential sin-
26 gular exceptions).

27 5.1.2 Functional difference

28 Chords are functionally different if they, or their equiva-
29 lents, are separated by a perfect fifth, as for example in
30 tonic-dominant or tonic-subdominant pairs, e.g. in authen-
31 tic or plagal progressions. Note, however, that pairs of
32 chords in the embedding space are undirected. In the ma-
33 jor mode (Figure 3), we find fifth-based relations between
34 chords in the embedding space for I: MAJ and V: MAJ;
35 I: AUG and V: AUG; III: MAJ and #II: DIM;¹ as well
36 as #IV: MAJ and #I: MAJ. In the minor mode (Fig-
37 ure 4), we find I: MIN and V: MAJ; II: MAJ and V: MIN;
38 #VI: MAJ/ MIN and #III: MIN; I: MAJ and IV: MIN;
39 as well as III: MAJ and VII: MAJ

40 It is notable that the main cadential chords in both modes
41 (i.e. triads on scale degrees I, V, IV, II, and VII in major,
42 and I, V, and II in minor) occur in relatively close proxim-
43 ity. Despite the fact that distances in embedding spaces are
44 generally hard to interpret, we take the ubiquity of relative,
45 parallel, subset, and fifths-based relations to be an indica-
46 tor for their pervasiveness in the harmonic progressions in
47 our corpus.

48 5.2 Chord prediction indicates historical differences 49 in harmonic styles

50 Here, we summarise the results obtained in chord predic-
51 tion. Since a composer’s prediction accuracy may change
52 for each run of our algorithm due to random initialization
53 of the Word2Vec and LSTM models, we run each exper-
54 iment ten times, and report mean and standard deviation
55 values for each composer. These are plotted in Figure 5,
56 per composer and mode, where each point represents the

¹ We interpret #II: DIM as a shortened VII: DOM7.

mean accuracy for all chords combined, and the shaded
bands show the standard deviation across the ten runs. The
composers are ordered by their year of death in order to
investigate historical trends.

The first thing to notice is that the standard deviations are
all quite small (< 0.04 in all cases), showing that our re-
sults are consistent across runs and are not affected by ran-
dom noise in the modeling process. Furthermore, the ap-
proximately “inverted U-shape” of the mean values implies
that Classical composers are the most predictable from our
data, followed by Baroque and Romantic composers, with
Modernist and Renaissance composers being the least pre-
dictable. This is not to say that Classical composers are
more predictable *in general* than composers from other
eras. Indeed, remembering that for each composer we
train on the data from all other composers in the corpus,
this trend is roughly implied by the distribution of data
shown in Figure 1. However, the very fact that such an
effect exists suggests that composers of the different eras
do use chords in fundamentally different ways. Since each
model is trained on a very similar set of data (differing by
only one composer), the learned model is necessarily sim-
ilar across composers. Therefore, if two composers used
chords similarly, their results would likewise be extremely
similar. So, the fact that we see a historical trend *at all*
suggests that composers of the different eras do indeed use
chords in fundamentally different ways (although we make
no claim here about what those differences are).

Furthermore, since the majority of our data comes from
Classical composers, we can hypothesize that the mean ac-
curacy of a composer should be positively correlated with
the similarity of that composer’s chord usage to that of
an average Classical composer. From this perspective, the
overall shape of the curve makes a lot of sense.

An analysis of the detailed per-chord accuracy results
(data available with the code), gives even more insight
about the idioms common to a specific composer or period.
The strongest result, in a major context, is the very low
prediction accuracy for I: MAJ and V: MAJ (the easiest
chords to predict overall) when testing on Ravel and De-
bussy. Indeed, they are two Impressionist composers, who
are generally known for their “distinct” harmonies, which
rarely (if ever) use authentic cadences. Moreover, we find
IV: MAJ and II: MIN to be two “polarising” chords: for
most composers, we either predict them very well or very
poorly compared to the average. In particular, IV: MAJ is
only well predictable for Baroque composers, while others
(with the exception of Beethoven, Chopin, and Dvořak)
seem to use it in a more peculiar way. II: MIN, on the
other hand, only becomes hard to predict from the late Ro-
mantic period. This latter result, albeit neat and striking,
is not as easily interpretable as the previous one. In mi-
nor sections, a low accuracy on I: MIN (the most com-
mon chord together with V: MAJ) for Renaissance com-
posers (Gesualdo, Sweelinck, Monteverdi, Schütz) and for
Modernists, again signals that this chord has played diverse
roles across the centuries. We achieve a relatively low ac-
curacy on many of the most common minor chords for both
Romantic and Modernist composers, with the exception

Figure 5. Global chord prediction accuracy for each composer, for major and minor sections. Standard deviation is given by the shaded region around each point. Composers are ordered chronologically by year of death.

of Tchaikovsky. This indicates that he is closer to Classical composers in his works in minor contexts (indeed, his only work in the dataset are the *Seasons*, a collection of rather traditional piano pieces overall). Changes in chord predictability related to stylistic differences are supported by historical studies focusing on the pitch-class content of musical pieces [25, 26].

6. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this paper, we investigated progressions of chords in both the major and minor mode by a number of different composers. Our study explored two applications of deep learning methods to music theory: which inferences about tonal relations between chords could be drawn from embedding them in a lower-dimensional space, and whether attempting to predict chords based on the regularities in the data would reveal stylistic differences between composers across historical periods. All data and code are available at <https://github.com/DCMLab/chordembeddings-smc2021>.

Word2Vec was our first processing step, which provided useful grounds to base our subsequent analyses on. When applied to the output vectors of Word2Vec, clustering could capture some well-known tonal relationships between chords, including relative, parallel, and subset relations, as well as (possibly transposed) tonic-dominant pairs of chords. On the other hand, LSTM-based chord prediction yielded fairly high accuracy results in general (roughly 50% for most composers), but it also allowed us to use

their high variability across chords and composers to draw some conclusions about chord usage across time which are supported by music theory. Globally, we found that Classical and Baroque composers use chords in a similar way, while Modernists and Renaissance composers seem to have a more distinctive style. The Romantic style seems to be complex, as there is a high variance in how composers from that era use chords.

Future work might also include a more refined use of clustering, for instance by applying it to a Word2Vec model trained only on a single composer—or on a group of composers which are known to be relatively similar to each other—in order to detect some special tonal relationship unique to that set of composers. Alternatively, chord prediction could be employed to investigate how rigidly a given composer belongs to a given artistic era: by restricting the training corpus to composers in the same era, we would prevent the model from learning totally unrelated idioms, thus achieving a higher accuracy on the test composer (to an extent depending on how similar he actually is to the others in that era).

As mentioned, in the current work, we identified the existence of historical differences in chord usage. However, we did not identify what those differences were. Future work could look at the problem from a more causal perspective by limiting the training corpus for each composer to only those composers who preceded them.

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